

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE IMPORTANCE OF TYLER-SOFRIN MODES
AS A SOURCE OF LOW ENGINE ORDER EXCITATION

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ABSTRACT

Current and new designs try to reduce the specific fuel consumption of the engine. These new designs lead to slender blades, more optimal from the aerodynamic point of view. Making the blade slender reduces its stiffness, so it is more prone to vibrate, impacting on the high cycle fatigue life. An accurate characterization of the different aeroelastic phenomena is required to reduce the uncertainty in predictions and making possible to move to slender blades.

Low Engine Order excitations are one type of disturbance with high influence on high cycle fatigue life. These perturbations are characterized by its low frequency hence they excite low structural modes in which low forcings can generate a high vibration due to the lower stiffness of these modes.

In this paper the aerodynamic interaction between static turbomachinery rows is studied. Under some conditions the scattered wave generated by the interaction, following Tyler & Sofrin theory, has an azimuthal wave number inside the low engine order range. Numerical simulation are carried out to give an insight on this type of disturbances, their nature, how they propagate between rows and the impact of manufacturing variability on them.

NOMENCLATURE

3D	Three dimensional
λ	Fluid Eigenvalues
ω	frequency (rad/s)
ξ	Critical damping ratio

AF	Amplitude-frequency (m·Hz)
CFD	Computation Fluid Dynamics
EO	Engine Order
F	Modal force (N)
f	Modal frequency (Hz)
FEM	Finite Element Method
GPU	Graphical Power Units
HCF	High Cycle Fatigue
k	Wave scatter index
LEO	Low Engine Order
LPT	Low Pressure Turbine
m	Azimuthal wave number
N	Number of airfoils of the row in which the wave is scattered
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
R	Rotor
RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes
S	Stator
TSM	Tyler-Sofrin Mode
U	Fluid flow variables
U-RANS	Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations
UNRBC	Unsteady Non-Reflective Boundary Conditions
δ_{mode}	Normalized maximum displacement
m_{mode}	Modal mass (kg)

Super-scripts

^	Harmonic amplitude
~	Unsteady field

Sub-scripts

A	Acoustic
C	Convective
n	Radial mode index
x	Axial position

1 INTRODUCTION

The different engine components are designed to fulfill a set of requirements related to high cycle fatigue (HCF) life. An accurate description of the excitation phenomena in a turbomachine will lead to better and more robust designs. One of the main types of disturbance from the point of view of HCF are the Low Engine Order (LEO) disturbances. They are synchronous perturbations of long azimuthal wavelength. The LEO disturbances excite the first structural modes due to their low frequency and are usually in the acoustic cut-on region or close to it [1], so the vibrations associated to these waves are generally large in terms of vibration amplitude.

The source of Low Engine Orders is one of the less understood phenomena in turbomachinery rows. The synchronous behavior suggests that they are due to the interaction between static and rotatory parts. Some authors try to relate this type of disturbances with phenomena such as Tyler & Sofrin modes (TSMs), geometric scatter, rubbing or rotordynamic effects [2]. The importance of each source depends on the particular application.

The manufacturing variability as a source of LEO excitations has been recently studied by various authors [3, 4, 5]. Even though the manufactured parts are inside tolerances, the geometric scatter between parts generates a loss of flow periodicity which results in long wavelength disturbances of small amplitude that modulate the periodic flow obtained by considering the nominal geometry.

The use of optical scans allows to consider the actual manufactured geometry, being possible to reproduce the manufactured turbomachinery row and the flow inhomogeneity caused by the small differences in geometry. Once the manufacturing variability has been characterized it is possible to perform probabilistic analyses to obtain the blade response [3]. Besides, some models have been developed to reconstruct the LEO disturbance. These models allow to reconstruct the change in the flow field due to the geometric scatter by running simplified simulations that involve a few passages and periodic flow conditions [4, 6]. These methods make feasible, both in time and computational resources, the use of Monte Carlo methods to characterize the aeroelastic response [6].

One of the main sources of unsteadiness in turbomachines are TSMs, relevant in noise generation [7]. These excitations are caused by the aerodynamic interaction between turbomachinery

rows, generating disturbance patterns with a wave number resulting from the combination of the number of airfoils of the different rows, being the importance of each interaction dependent on the actual case. TSMs have been observed experimentally and numerically [8, 9]. From the point of view of LEO, stator rows with similar number of airfoils can interact generating low azimuthal wave number disturbances which are stationary in the absolute frame but act as unsteady in the rotor frame. To numerically reproduce this phenomenon, methods based on non-linear harmonics or harmonic balance methods have been recently developed [10, 11, 12]. Although this phenomenon has been deeply studied in the field of aerodynamics [13], the available works about dynamic response of LEO originated by aerodynamic interaction is limited [9, 14].

In this work a numerical study of the TSMs as a source of LEO disturbances is carried out. It takes into account the aerodynamic interaction between different rows in a low pressure turbine (LPT), explaining the generation mechanism and how the wave is propagated through the turbomachine. To conclude, the manufacturing variability of one stator row is considered, performing a stochastic analysis and showing the impact of this geometric scatter in the generated TSMs.

2 METHODOLOGY

The main goal of this research is to show that the interaction between static parts can be a source of LEO disturbances. A numerical study is carried out using $\text{Mu}^2\text{s}^2\text{t}$ [15], the in-house CFD solver developed by ITP Aero. The flow field is obtained as a combination of a steady flow field, computed using RANS methodology, and a small disturbance field that is obtained solving the linearized U-RANS equations [16]. The unsteady pressure field is projected into the structural modes obtaining the structural response [17].

Steady Flow Field

$\text{Mu}^2\text{s}^2\text{t}$ solves the RANS equations in the relative frame of reference. It uses a finite volume formulation on semi-structured grids storing the conservative variables on the cell vertex, calculating fluxes with Roe scheme. It allows explicit or implicit time integration and different turbulence models. The code is parallelized and optimized to run using GPUs [18]. Mixing-plane formulation [19] is employed to compute the multi-row steady flow.

Unsteady Flow Field

The linear solver $\text{Mu}^2\text{s}^2\text{t-L}$ computes the unsteady linearized solution of 3D RANS equations in the frequency domain. It assumes frozen turbulence and uses similar algorithms to the steady RANS solver to ensure the consistency between solutions.

FIGURE 1. Multi-row linear simulation scheme.

It has been widely used to study the aerodynamic interaction between rows in noise studies and flutter analyses [20, 21].

An extension of the linear solver was developed to be able to perform multi-row simulations, transmitting the linearized unsteady field to the different rows through the mixing planes [21].

First of all the disturbance to analyze is selected (wake harmonic, potential field...). This initial wave has an azimuthal wave number m_0 and according to Tyler and Sofrin theory, it can get scattered when it interacts with a row of N airfoils following:

$$m_k = m_0 + kN, k = \dots, -1, 0, 1, \dots \quad (1)$$

Being N the number of airfoils of the row in which the disturbance is scattered and k the index of the scattering, so $k=0$ corresponds to the unscattered original wave. The wave number of the input disturbance and its frequency is known in advance and its amplitude and radial profile is obtained by performing a Fourier analysis of the steady solution. This disturbance is injected as input in the corresponding mixing-plane and is previously filtered by the solver, so that only the part that should propagate inside the row is imposed.

For the linear multi-row simulation both the input wave and their scatters (Tyler & Sofrin modes) can be transmitted between rows as it is shown in Figure 1, allowing to consider the reflection of the waves in other rows. 3D UNRBC are imposed to the waves non-transmitted between rows at the row interfaces. It requires to decompose the unsteady flow into travelling waves by performing Fourier decomposition at different radial positions:

$$\tilde{U}(x, r, \theta, t) = \sum_k \hat{U}_k(x, r) e^{i(m_k \theta - \omega t)} \quad (2)$$

These travelling waves known as 'spinning modes' are broken down into acoustic and nearly convected waves, being possible to decompose the acoustic field into upstream and downstream propagating waves, following a formulation similar to

[22]. A wave-splitting decomposition is applied to the linear flow field in each mixing plane, allowing the transference of information between rows and the use of 3D non-reflective boundary conditions. More information can be found in [17].

Vibration amplitude

The vibration amplitude is computed from the unsteady pressure field acting on the airfoils. A linear response is assumed in this work, following an uncoupled formulation [17].

The modal force F for each structural mode is obtained by projecting the unsteady pressure field obtained in the linear simulation into the vibrating mode-shape of the airfoil.

The structural modes are calculated using ITP's in house FEM solver, Xipetotec [23]. The structural modes are obtained in travelling wave form by performing a pre-stressed FEM modal analysis with cyclic symmetry boundary conditions, being the pre-stressed state the result of a previous static structural simulation.

The value of the total critical damping ratio ξ is fixed for each structural mode. In this work a representative constant value of 1% is considered for all the modes of interest.

To compare the HCF impact of each vibrating mode the AF parameter is used (maximum displacement x modal frequency) instead of the vibration amplitude. This parameter is widely used to asses HCF [24]. For lightly damped systems under harmonic excitation the AF in resonant conditions can be calculated as:

$$AF = \frac{F}{2 \cdot \xi \cdot m_{mode} \cdot (2\pi f)^2} \cdot \delta_{mode} \cdot f \quad (3)$$

Being m_{mode} the modal mass, f the modal frequency and δ_{mode} the maximum modal displacement in the structural mode.

3 ANALYSIS CASE

The case studied in the paper consist of three stages of a realistic LPT as it is shown in Figure 2. The central stage, referred as 0, is the one in which the vibration is analyzed and it is the same geometry used in our previous LEO studies due to manufacturing variability [5, 6]. One stage has been added upstream and downstream to study the aerodynamic interaction between static rows. The effect of the TSM modes on aeroelastic response is evaluated in the central blade row (R_0) computing its vibration amplitude.

The difference in the number of airfoils in the stator rows is low ($N_{S_1} - N_{S_0} = 4$, $N_{S_0} - N_{S_1} = 6$, $N_{S_1} - N_{S_1} = 10$), so the aerodynamic interaction between them generates disturbances inside the LEO range.

The mesh size is between 6M-8M of nodes per passage depending on the row. The walls (blades and casings) are meshed

FIGURE 2. Three stages of LPT used in the research.

to fulfill $y^+ < 1$ requirement to properly describe the boundary layer evolution. The mesh density in the azimuthal direction is chosen depending on the azimuthal wave number to simulate, since a minimum number of points per wave-length is needed for an accurate generation and transmission of the disturbance. The same mesh is used for all the analyses so the number of points in the azimuthal direction is selected according to the shortest wave-length to simulate.

4 TYLER-SOFRIN INTERACTION MODES

TSMs are generated by the aerodynamic interaction between rows. In this case the interactions $S_{-1} - S_0$, $S_0 - S_1$ and $S_{-1} - S_1$ are studied. The stator's wake propagates downstream, interacting with the other rows. On the other hand acoustic disturbances associated to the potential field can propagate upstream and downstream. The wave number of these disturbances is related to the number of airfoils in the row that generates them and they can get scattered in other stator, generating a perturbation with a wave number resulting of the difference in the number of airfoils between rows. The airfoil count in the static rows is close enough to consider the interaction mode as LEO. The LEOs generated by the interaction mechanisms previously explained excite the low structural modes of R_0 row inside the operating range, as it is shown in Figure 3, so they have to be considered in the HCF analysis of the turbomachine.

These LEO disturbances are close to the acoustic cut-on region, hence these disturbances are expected to propagate along

FIGURE 3. Campbell diagram for R_0 blade-disk.

the turbine with a low decay ratio, as a consequence they could generate high response on the different blade rows. This work tries to give an answer about how many blade rows are prone to be affected by this source of LEO.

The EO associated to the number of airfoils is above 100 in all the cases, so the acoustic component associated to these waves has a high decay ratio. CFD simulations show that acoustics propagating upstream do not reach upstream stator with enough amplitude to generate significant TSMs. The mechanism studied as a source of TSMs is the acoustic and vorticity waves (associated to potential field and wakes) propagating downstream and scattered in the following stator rows.

The unsteady flow is simulated as follows:

1. Steady flow is calculated with a mixing plane methodology.
2. The downstream disturbance source of LEO is previously selected and the input disturbance is obtained carrying out a Fourier decomposition of the steady solution. This original disturbance (m_0) is the input for the multi-row linear simulation.
3. The input wave is propagated along the whole turbine and the interaction mode with one of the downstream stator rows, obtained using $k=-1$ in the equation 1, is propagated upstream and downstream.

Finally, the solution is post-processed, splitting the disturbance into acoustic and vorticity component, showing how it is transmitted along the fluid domain and the unsteady pressure field on the blades' surface and computing the vibration amplitude of R_0 blades.

FIGURE 4. Eigenvalues for EO 4 at R_0 outlet patch.

4.1 Interaction between S_{-1} and S_0

In this case the interaction between the wave associated to the number of airfoils in S_{-1} and S_0 generates a LEO with an azimuthal wave number of 4, result of the scatter with $k = -1$ according to equation 1.

For a deeper understanding of the physics involved in wave propagation is useful to break down into components the unsteady flow associated to a spinning mode. This task can be performed by solving a linear generalized eigenvalue problem and can be applied to any axisymmetric and axially uniform flow [22].

As a result of the mode decomposition, acoustic modes, which represent the majority of the pressure content, and nearly convected waves, dominated by entropy and vorticity perturbations are obtained [21]. Hence the unsteady flow can be represented as the sum of acoustic and nearly convected fields: $\hat{U}_m(x, r) = \hat{U}_{A,m}(x, r) + \hat{U}_{C,m}(x, r)$. The acoustic modes can be further decomposed into radial upstream and downstream propagating modes:

$$\hat{U}_{A,m}(x, r) = \sum_n c_{m,n}^+ u_{m,n}^+(r) e^{i\lambda_{x,m,n}^+ x} + \sum_n c_{m,n}^- u_{m,n}^-(r) e^{i\lambda_{x,m,n}^- x} \quad (4)$$

The decomposition helps to explain how the waves propagate through the fluid field. Nearly convected waves travel downstream and their amplitude do not decay with the propagation, as long as acoustic waves propagate upstream and downstream. Regarding the axial wave number $\lambda_{x,m,n}$, an acoustic radial mode can propagate without decay if $\lambda_{x,m,n}$ is real (cut-on modes) or show an exponential decay in amplitude if $\lambda_{x,m,n}$ is complex (cut-off modes). The eigenmode decomposition of the flow at R_0 outlet is shown in Figure 4.

The interaction between the potential field of S_0 with S_{-1} would generate a wave with the same azimuthal pattern, but the

FIGURE 5. Unsteady pressure distribution on R_0 . Left vorticity contribution and right acoustic one.

intensity of the acoustics that reach S_{-1} is too low to contribute significantly to the LEO. Since the decay rate of acoustics upstream and downstream is similar (value of the imaginary part of each eigenpair) it is expected that the source of this wave is the scatter of the convective components, in this particular case the vorticity one.

The unsteady pressure associated to the LEO generated will be a combination of two sources: vorticity and acoustics. Both components are shown in Figure 5. The vorticity component is concentrated at the secondary flow region. Although the pressure peak is higher for the vorticity wake, the order of magnitude of the acoustic one is the same, so it is expected that both of them have importance on the aeroelastic response. This decomposition is performed for all the cases studied, so everytime we talk about acoustic or vorticity wave we refer to each of the components of the disturbance obtained through the wave-splitting technique explained above.

One of the goals of this study is to show how TSMs affect the whole turbine, that is, if the disturbance originated by the aerodynamic interaction between stator rows can produce vibration response in rotor rows far away from the generating row. Figure 6 illustrates how the acoustics propagate through the different turbine rows. In this graphic the amplitude of the three first acoustic radial modes, downstream (+) and upstream (-), associated to EO 4 are plotted. The acoustic component is important in the rotor rows close to the stator that generates the TSM, since the amplitude of this wave decreases with the propagation and the reflections in other rows. Only the first radial mode, which is the closest one to cut-on condition (Figure 4), reaches other rotor

FIGURE 6. Acoustic radial modes amplitude along axial position.

rows with significant amplitude, although it is roughly four times lower than its amplitude on the rotors adjacent to the generator stator. So it is possible that the acoustics are only important in the closest rotor rows, neglecting the upstream rotors from the closest one upstream.

Another point to study is if the analysis can be limited to the closest rotor downstream too. In this case the vorticity component has to be considered too. The radial profile of the velocity associated to the vorticity wave is shown in Figure 7. The vorticity component of the disturbance that propagates downstream is shown in S_0 - R_0 mixing plane. Vorticity can only propagate downstream, so attending to R_{-1} - S_0 mixing plane, it seems that there is some trade between acoustics and vorticity, it means that part of the acoustics propagating upstream is reflected as vorticity. This disturbance is convected downstream, and when it reaches R_1 (S_1 - R_1 mixing plane) it has been partially attenuated, but it can not be ensured that the wave amplitude will not be high enough to make R_1 vibrate noticeably.

The amplitude of the vorticity and acoustic component has been shown but it necessary to translate it to unsteady pressure acting on the blade surface since it is the forcing which generates the vibration. According to Figure 5, acoustic and convective components are of the same order of magnitude, so the unsteady pressure it is expected to be higher in the closest downstream rotor (R_0). The upstream rotor (R_{-1}) is only affected by the acoustic wave; although the unsteady pressure is lower that in R_0 it is not negligible. Regarding R_1 it can be seen that the wave is attenuated as it propagates downstream, both for the decay of the amplitude of the acoustic wave and for the decrease of the vorticity component due to reflections and wave scatter. Even so, it shows a significant level of unsteady pressure acting on it as it is illustrated in Figure 8, so it seems that TSMs may produce

FIGURE 7. Radial profile of the modulus of the unsteady velocity associated to vorticity at mixing plane axial location.

FIGURE 8. Unsteady pressure field on rotor stage airfoils due to S_{-1} - S_0 interaction. Left R_{-1} , center R_0 and right R_1 .

vibrations in rotor rows downstream beyond the contiguous one.

4.2 Interaction between S_0 and S_1

Another case to study is the interaction between S_0 and S_1 , which generates a wave of an azimuthal number of 6. As it occurs in the case explained in section 4.1 the interaction between the potential field of S_1 and S_0 is negligible, therefore only the disturbance associated to the number of airfoils of S_0 (acoustic and convective) that travels downstream and is scattered on S_1 with scatter index $k=-1$ is considered.

FIGURE 9. Acoustic radial modes amplitude along axial position.

FIGURE 10. Radial profile of the modulus of the unsteady velocity associated to vorticity at mixing plane axial location.

This case is interesting from the point of view of acoustics propagating upstream. In this case the acoustic wave amplitude is also higher in the rotor rows close to the TSMs generator row, as it is expected since the acoustic decay with the propagation as it is shown in Figure 9. When the wave reaches an airfoil row one fraction is reflected, other is transmitted and another one is scattered in a different wave number. It explains the gaps in the amplitude of the radial modes through the rows. Second and third radial modes decrease faster than the first one since their cut-off ratio is higher, being its amplitude negligible beyond the R_0 and R_1 rows. The first radial mode is near cut-on condition, hence its amplitude barely decreases with the propagation. This acoustic mode could affect all the stages.

FIGURE 11. Unsteady pressure field on rotor stage airfoils due to S_0 - S_1 interaction. Left R_{-1} , center R_0 and right R_1 .

The amplitude of the vorticity component is studied in this case too. Its amplitude is higher in the mixing plane downstream the TSMs generator row (S_1 - R_1) in the same way that in the previous case (Figure 10). The vorticity component that appears in R_0 - S_1 mixing plane is the result of the reflection of the acoustic wave on R_0 . In the same way that the EO 4 case, the vorticity component is convected downstream, being its amplitude comparable to the one at the rows closest to the generator row so it is possible it makes rotor rows beyond the first rotor row downstream vibrate.

Figure 11 shows the unsteady pressure distribution on the blade rows. The results are aligned with the one obtained for S_{-1} - S_0 interaction, the major contribution to the unsteady pressure field seems to be the vorticity component as it is shown in the figure. Attending to blade R_1 , the unsteady pressure peaks are located at hub and tip area, coincident with the secondary flow cores. The acoustic component is relevant in the first upstream rotor, but it is much lower in R_{-1} , hence it seems that the TSMs have a limited effect upstream.

4.3 Interaction between S_{-1} and S_1

The previous sections try to answer how the information propagates through the different rows and which rows can be affected by the TSMs generated. The importance of the generation of LEO due to the interaction between not adjacent stator rows is studied in this section.

The disturbance that reaches S_1 is dominated by the vorticity component, generating a TSM of EO 10. This component is lower than the one that reaches S_0 because of wave reflections

FIGURE 12. Acoustic radial modes amplitude along axial position.

FIGURE 13. Unsteady pressure field on rotor stage airfoils due to S_{-1} - S_1 interaction. Left R_{-1} , center R_0 and right R_1 .

and scatters in S_0 and R_0 and the transmission through them, so the acoustics generated by the interaction S_1 - S_{-1} is lower than the ones generated by S_1 - S_0 as it is shown in Figure 6 and 12. One interesting finding is that the vorticity component is reflected mainly as third acoustic radial mode; it is due to the radial shape of this acoustic mode which has two nodes.

In this case, acoustic perturbations are predominantly generated in high (>3) radial modes. The greatest the acoustic mode the greatest the decay ratio for cut-off acoustic modes, so the

FIGURE 14. Unsteady pressure field on R_0 airfoil surface. Left EO 4, center EO 6, Right EO 10.

decay of the acoustics in this case will be higher than in the previous ones, so it is not expected that the acoustic wave reaches rows beyond the adjacent ones to S_1 .

According to Figure 13 the dominant component is the vorticity one too, hence it is possible that it generates unsteady pressure level high enough to make downstream rotors vibrate.

4.4 Aeroelastic response

In previous sections the interaction mechanisms between the three stator rows have been explained. All of them generate a non-negligible unsteady pressure field on the blade of study (R_0), so it is important to translate it into aeroelastic response.

From the point of view of HCF life a main parameter is the AF parameter, that can be understood as a vibration velocity, since it takes into account the vibration amplitude and the frequency of the vibration. This parameter is calculated for each interaction mechanism at R_0 blade row (Figure 14).

All the crossings in the operating range according to Campbell diagram (Figure 3) have been considered. Each resonance is analyzed at the operating conditions for the crossing and a constant critical damping ratio of 1%, representative of this configuration, has been assumed for all the cases.

The AF results are shown in Figure 15. According to the unsteady pressure fields plotted in Figure 14 EO 4 and 6 generates a forcing in all the airfoil surface as long as the forcing is concentrated at hub area for EO 10. At low structural modes the blade movement is concentrated at tip, so it can explain the low AF obtained for EO 10. Furthermore the EO 10 perturbation was small. For the other cases the AF obtained is high and has to be

FIGURE 15. Normalized AF for each resonance and interaction mode at R_0 .

considered in HCF life calculus.

The value of vibration amplitude in terms of AF is comparable to the one due to the manufacturing variability in S_0 [6]. The mean value of the response due to the manufacturing variability obtained with a Monte Carlo simulation is 0.15 for the first structural mode and 0.08 for the second one. This highlights the importance of the TSMs, which can be one of the sources of LEO disturbances.

5 MANUFACTURING VARIABILITY EFFECTS ON TYLER-SOFRIN MODES

Some published works [3, 4, 5, 6] have studied how the manufacturing scatter can be a source of LEO disturbances but, in our knowledge, there is no available research about how this variability affects to the wake harmonics and the Tyler-Sofrin interaction modes.

In this case realistic deviations based on manufactured parts, consistent with the results from [5, 6], are applied to stator row S_0 , which creates differences between the wakes of the airfoils in the row and its potential field, so the amplitude associated to the EO related to the number of airfoils will differ from the tuned case, and this discrepancies are translated into a change in the interaction modes amplitude.

The manufacturing variability is characterized from a set of optical scans of the casted parts. The scans are imported into ITP Aeros's design system, being the 3D geometry defined as a set of radial sections to which a PCA analysis is performed to reduce the dimensionality of the problem. More detailed information about the process can be found in [5].

Once the manufacturing variability has been characterized the aerodynamic forcing can be computed. A random row is

FIGURE 16. Variation in AF of R_0 for S_0 - S_1 interaction due to manufacturing variability.

generated from the average airfoils and the geometric modes obtained with the PCA algorithm. The changes in the flow due to the geometric variability is calculated using the fluid flow reconstruction algorithm explained in [6]. A Fourier analysis of the reconstructed fluid field is performed, obtaining the aerodynamic forcing for the EO associated to the number of airfoils in S_0 .

This aerodynamic forcing is used as input in the lineal multi-row simulation, studying the interaction between S_0 and S_1 in the same way done for the design intent geometry in section 4.2. The changes in geometry are only considered to calculate the input for the simulation, in the simulation the design geometry is considered since they only have influence on the reflections of the waves.

The manufacturing variability is a stochastic phenomenon, so it must be analyzed with probabilistic simulation. In this case Monte Carlo methods are employed to build a set of 100 random S_0 rows, generating 100 aerodynamic forcing cases. The unsteady pressure on R_0 airfoil surface is projected into its structural modes inside the operating range, obtaining the modal force value used to compute the AF parameter.

Figure 16 shows the probability distribution of the aeroelastic response for this interaction. More than 80% of the cases lie into -2.5% to $+5\%$ of the one obtained with the nominal tuned geometry. It can be concluded that the manufacturing variability introduces a small correction in the interaction mode but this correction is small enough to be neglected and use the AF obtained without considering the manufacturing variability in the HCF assessment.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Along this work the aerodynamic interaction between static rows as source of LEO has been numerically studied using a ge-

ometry representative of three stages LPT. The interaction mechanism described by Tyler and Sofrin can generate low frequency waves when the number of airfoils of the static rows is close enough.

First, the design geometry is used to study all the interaction between static rows pairs. These interactions generate disturbances of azimuthal wave number 4, 6 and 10. The goal of the interaction analysis is to demonstrate that the Tyler-Sofrin modes can be a source of LEO and to give an insight about how many rows can be affected by these disturbances.

The main findings of the first part are:

- The interaction modes can be a source of LEO. The AF obtained for this mechanism (Figure 15) is of the same order of magnitude that the one associated to manufacturing variability [6], so this additional source must be taken into account along with the geometric variability in the HCF assessment.
- Regarding the results, it seems that the interaction modes has non-negligible influence on the first rotor upstream the row that generates the TSM.
- In downstream rotors is not clear how many rows beyond the first one will be affected. The vorticity component is convected downstream and can reach the different rotors with enough amplitude to make it vibrate, so it needs further research on this topic.
- Interaction modes can be generated between non-contiguous stator rows since vorticity is the main component of the wave that is scattered to generate the TSM. In this particular case the response generated is negligible, but it depends on the case.

The second part of the paper aims to quantify the effects of manufacturing variability on TSM. Manufacturing scatter has been considered for S_0 stator row, which changes the amplitude of the wave that generates the TSM, so the aerodynamic interaction with S_{-1} row varies too.

The manufacturing scatter has been shown to cause a small variation on the TSM and in consequence in the AF calculated for R_0 row. The AF value obtained with the design geometry is a good approximation to the mean value considering manufacturing dispersion (-2.5% to $+5\%$) so this variability on casted parts can be neglected in fatigue studies for these type of interactions.

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